

Hydrogen atom addition to d^8 complexes of nickel, palladium and platinum

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Dilute solutions of $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ and $\text{Pt}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ in methanol-water glasses at 77 K give, on exposure to ionizing radiation EPR spectra, assigned to $\text{H}^\bullet\text{-M}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ derivatives. The very large ^1H hyperfine splittings show that the unpaired electron must be in an $\text{M}^\bullet\text{-H } \sigma^*$ orbital. The initial species are the electron adducts, $\text{M}(\text{CN})_4^{3-}$, but on annealing, features for these protonated anions grow in. However, the palladium complex gives a different derivative, with relatively small ^1H hyperfine splitting. This is thought to be the result of a rearrangement putting the excess electron into the d -manifold of the metal, so that the ligand becomes a normal hydride ligand. So far as I know, these metal hydrides are unique in transition metal chemistry.

The hydride ion, H^- , is the simplest ligand in transition metal chemistry. Its complexes can be formed by H^- addition, H^\bullet addition or H^+ addition to the metal centre. However, in practice, H^- or H^+ addition have been studied extensively, but H^\bullet atom addition has been neglected¹.

In the above cases, the ligand should be viewed as being H^- , in accord with normal convention. All the known species formed by H^- or H^+ addition have small or negative spin density on the hydrogen ligand. Thus, these complexes are quite different from those formed by H^\bullet atom addition. In most of the EPR studies of these hydrido complexes, the ^1H hyperfine coupling has been small^{2,3}. However, in our studies of the $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ adduct, a very large proton splitting was detected⁴. Comparable splittings were found for the platinum complex, and the ^{195}Pt hyperfine splitting confirmed that the spin-density on platinum was also very large. The form of the g -tensor showed that the SOMO comprised a mixture of s and d_{z^2} orbitals on platinum⁵.

At about the same time, Morton and Preston studied the complex $\text{H-Co}(\text{CO})_4$ and showed that this also has high spin-densities on hydrogen and cobalt⁶. They went on to show that the nickel complex formed from $\text{Ni}(\text{CO})_4$ had lost one of the CO ligands on hydrogen addition⁷. They therefore suggested that our complex, thought to be $\text{H}^\bullet\text{-Ni}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$, was really $\text{H}^\bullet\text{-Ni}(\text{CN})_3$. However, in our view, this is improbable for the primary centre detected. This is discussed below.

Results and Discussion

Results for the nickel, palladium and platinum derivatives are given in Table 1 together with other pertinent data. Typical EPR spectral data for the $\text{H}^\bullet\text{-Pt}$ and $\text{H}^\bullet\text{-Pd}$ derivatives are given in Tables 1 and 2, together with stick diagrams showing pertinent features. Extra features assigned

Table 1. Some EPR parameters for relevant transition metal hydrides

Compd.	^1H hyperfine coupling/ $G^{a,b}$			Metal hyperfine coupling			Ref.
	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	A_{iso}	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	A_{iso}	
$\text{H}^\bullet\text{-Ni}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$	–	–	153.6	–	–	–	4
$\text{H}^\bullet\text{-Pt}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$	182	172	175.3	409	–90	76.3	5
$\text{H-Co}(\text{CO})_4$	–	–	53.6	66.8	–28.6	–9.6	6
$\text{H-Ni}(\text{CO})_3$	–	–	105.6	79	53	61.7	7

^a $1G = 10^{-4} T$. ^bThe hyperfine couplings are corrected for Δg . ^c g -values in the region of 2.1 for g_{\parallel} and 1.99 for g_{\perp} .

Table 2. EPR parameters for centres derived from $\text{Pd}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ ions

Compd.	^1H hyperfine coupling ^a (iso)	^{105}Pd hyperfine coupling		
		A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	A_{iso}
$\text{PdH}(\text{CN})_3$ or $\text{PdH}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$	45.6	14	14	–4.5

^a g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} in the region of 2 and 1.99 for g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} .

to the primary electron adduct, $\text{Pd}(\text{CN})_4^{3-}$, were also detected.

Interpretation of spectra :

The yields of the hydrido derivative for the platinum complex were much higher than that for the palladium derivative, and hence spectral interpretation was easier. The key to understanding these spectra came from comparison between the $\text{H}^\bullet\text{-Pt}$ and $\text{D}^\bullet\text{-Pt}$ derivatives⁵. Complications arose because the $+1/2$ ^{195}Pt perpendicular feature was almost as intense as those from the non-magnetic isotopes. We concluded that this was, in fact, a false turning point, and hence were able to obtain good hyperfine data (Table 1).

However, when solutions of $\text{Pd}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ were used, the expected monomer species, $\text{H}^\bullet\text{-Pd}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ was not detected. Instead, a novel centre with EPR spectra similar to those for

Fig. 1. EPR spectrum assigned to the $\text{H}^{\cdot}\text{Pt}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ complex (from Ref. 5): (a) experimental, (b) simulation.

normal transition-metal hydrides was detected (Fig. 2). I suggest that the expected parent σ^* -unit had either isomerised to give $\text{PdH}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ or lost CN^- to give $\text{PdH}(\text{CN})_3$. Why this change is only favoured for the Pd-derivative is not clear.

Fig. 2. EPR spectrum assigned to the $\text{Pd}(\text{H})(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ or $\text{Pd}(\text{H})(\text{CN})_3^{2-}$ complex

Aspects of structure :

These results suggest that the $\text{H}^{\cdot}\text{Ni}$ and $\text{H}^{\cdot}\text{Pt}$ complexes have the same structures. The spin-density is strongly confined to the σ^* H-M bond, as shown in Table 3. Herein, approximate spin-densities have been estimated from the calculated values of the hyperfine splittings for unit population, in the usual way⁸. This method always gives a good first order measure of spin-distributions in radicals and paramagnetic metal complexes.

The parent $d^8 \text{M}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$ complexes are square-planar, with two electrons in the d_{z^2} orbital. The attacking hydrogen atom moves initially onto this orbital to give a σ^* -com-

Table 3. Some estimated spin-densities

Compd.	Spin-density on ^1H	Spin-density on M
$\text{H}^{\cdot}\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$	0.30	-
$\text{H}^{\cdot}\text{Pd}(\text{CN})_3$ or $\text{H}^{\cdot}\text{Pd}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$	0.09	0.36
$\text{H}^{\cdot}\text{Pt}(\text{CN})_4^{2-}$	0.36	0.80
$\text{H}^{\cdot}\text{Co}(\text{CO})_4$	0.11	0.50
$\text{H}^{\cdot}\text{Ni}(\text{CO})_3$	0.21	0.41

plex. Although such complexes are important in radical chemistry, and have been widely studied by EPR spectroscopy⁹, they are rare in transition-metal chemistry. So far as I know, these hydrides are unique. They closely resemble the hydrogen adducts of halide ions, $\text{H}^{\cdot}\text{hal}^-$, that we have previously studied¹⁰. These $\text{H}^{\cdot}\text{hal}^-$ radicals have higher spin-densities on the hydrogen atoms because of the high electronegativities of the halide ions. This constrains the σ -bonding electrons towards the halide ions, thereby pushing the unpaired electron onto hydrogen. In the present cases, the electrons are more symmetrically arranged.

Aspects of mechanism :

When solutions in methanol or methanol-water glasses are used, the electron-loss centres are trapped by the solvent, but the ejected electrons migrate through the glasses and either become trapped in solvent vacancies or add to an electron-affinic solute, S, to give $\text{S}^{\cdot-}$ radicals.

Thus, for the present systems, the d^9 -complexes, $\text{M}(\text{CN})_4^{3-}$ are formed. These have a SOMO (semi-occupied molecular orbital) comprising the fully antibonding metal $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals and the σ -orbitals of the CN^- ligands. These anions have high proton affinities, and readily add protons to the available d_{z^2} orbitals. In order to form the σ^* -complexes, it is now necessary for the unpaired electron to migrate from the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital into the σ^* -orbital. This is a subtle issue but is clearly favourable since the extent of antibonding is reduced.

For the methanolic glasses, it is important that the intense violet-black colours formed on irradiation in the absence of any solute, were not formed for dilute solutions of the cyanide complexes. Thus, electron-addition to these complexes is facile. These may now protonate, and then lose CN^- ions on annealing. For the palladium complex, a novel species with small proton hyperfine splitting was detected. The ^{105}Pd hyperfine data and the g -values show that this has a normal $d_{z^2}^{1/2}$ structure. Hence the hydrogen must have moved into the xy -plane. The simplest mechanism would be for one cyanide ligand to move into the sixth site with the hydride ligand taking its place. However, it may be that one of the cyanide ligands is lost completely.

Experimental

$K_2Pd(CN)_4$ and $K_2Pt(CN)_4$ (Strem Chemicals, Fluorochem Ltd.) were used without further purification.

Dilute glasses in CD_3OD (or CH_3OH) + H_2O or + D_2O were obtained as beads in EPR tubes, with the exclusion of oxygen. These were exposed to ^{60}Co γ -rays in a Vickrad source at 77 K for up to 1 Mrad doses. Spectra were measured at 77 K using a Varian E109 spectrometer, with low modulation frequencies. Samples were annealed in the cavity, and recooled to 77 K whenever spectral changes were detected.

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